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MODERN CONCEPTS IN LUMBAR SYNDROME THERAPY:
A REVIEW OF LITERATUREIvica Lalić¹, Oliver Dulić^{2,3}, Branko Baljak^{2,3}, Marko Bojović^{2,4},
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SAŽETAK

Lumbalni bolni sindrom (LBS) obuhvata bolne senzacije u predelu lumbalnog ili lumbosakralnog dela kičmenog stuba, koje mogu, ali ne moraju, biti praćene širenjem bola u donje ekstremitete. Lumbalni bol je značajan javnozdravstveni problem u industrijalizovanim zemljama. Smatra se da je ovaj sindrom čest uzrok radne nesposobnosti kod preko 25% osoba mlađih od 45 godina, pri čemu u razvijenim zemljama često dolazi do dugotrajnih bolovanja (više od 90 izgubljenih radnih dana). Ovim pregledom smo imali za cilj da istražimo i analiziramo efikasnost rehabilitacionih metoda u tretmanu pacijenata sa lumbalnim sindromom. Poseban fokus je stavljen na ulogu fizikalne terapije i specifičnih vežbi koje pomažu u smanjenju bola, povećanju funkcionalnosti i prevenciji ponovnog javljanja problema. U ovom radu analizirani su različiti aspekti lumbalnog sindroma, uključujući kliničku sliku, dijagnostičke metode i terapijske mogućnosti. Poseban akcenat stavljen je na značaj individualizovanog terapijskog pristupa, koji uključuje medikamentnu terapiju, fizikalne i manuelne tehnike, kao i edukaciju pacijenata. Dokazi ukazuju na to da kombinacija različitih modaliteta lečenja pruža najbolje rezultate, omogućavajući smanjenje bola, povećanje mobilnosti i dugoročno smanjenje učestalosti recidiva. Lumbalni sindrom zahteva sveobuhvatan i multidisciplinarni pristup, a pravilno vođenje pacijenata doprinosi ne samo poboljšanju njihovog zdravstvenog stanja, već i smanjenju ukupnog opterećenja na zdravstveni sistem. Ova studija pruža osnovu za dalju primenu savremenih terapijskih strategija i promoviše holistički pristup u upravljanju ovim kompleksnim zdravstvenim problemom.

Ključne reči: lumbalni sindrom, rehabilitacija, fizikalna terapija, medikamentna terapija

SUMMARY

Lumbar pain syndrome (LPS) includes painful sensations in the area of the lumbar or lumbosacral part of the spinal column, which may or may not be accompanied by the spread of pain to the lower extremities. Low back pain is a significant public health problem in industrialized countries. It is considered that this syndrome is a common cause of work incapacity in over 25% of people under the age of 45, and in developed countries it often results in long-term sick leave (more than 90 lost working days). With this review, we aimed to investigate and analyze the effectiveness of rehabilitation methods in the treatment of patients with lumbar syndrome. A special focus is placed on the role of physical therapy and specific exercises that help reduce pain, increase functionality, and prevent recurrence of problems. This paper analyzes various aspects of lumbar syndrome, including the clinical picture, diagnostic methods, and therapeutic possibilities. Special emphasis is placed on the importance of an individualized therapeutic approach, including drug therapy, physical and manual techniques, and patient education. Evidence suggests that a combination of different treatment modalities provides the best results, allowing for pain reduction, increased mobility, and long-term reduction in recurrence rates. Lumbar syndrome requires a comprehensive and multidisciplinary approach, and proper management of patients contributes not only to improving their health, but also to reducing the overall burden on the healthcare system. This study provides a basis for further application of modern therapeutic strategies and promotes a holistic approach in the management of this complex health problem.

Keywords: lumbar syndrome, rehabilitation, physical therapy, drug therapy

Introduction

Lumbar pain syndrome (LPS) includes painful sensations in the area of the lumbar or lumbosacral part of the spinal column, which may or may not be accompanied by the spread of pain to the lower extremities. Accurate diagnosis of this syndrome is crucial, as it is often accompanied by dysfunction of the lumbosacral segment of the spine, protective spasms of the muscles, as well as possible sensibility disorders [1]. Pain in the lumbosacral region, which in our country is called a lumbar syndrome, includes terms such as lumbar discopathy, lumbago, lumboschialgia, sciatica, compressive lumbar syndrome, and others. In the international literature, the most common expressions for this phenomenon are low back pain, lumbar syndrome, lumbago, lumbalgia, and similar terms [2].

According to epidemiological data, 9.2% of the world's population is affected by low back pain, while the prevalence ranges from 49-70%. In developed countries, as many as 70% of people suffer from low back pain during their lifetime, and this percentage can reach 80% [3]. Specific low back pain accounts for only 15% of all back pain problems. In comparison, 50% of specific Incomparision pain is caused by intervertebral disc prolapse, where the nucleus pulposus passes through the annulus fibrosus, causing nerve root irritation and radicular pain [4].

Low back pain is a significant public health problem in industrialized countries [5]. It is considered that this syndrome is a common cause of work incapacity in over 25% of people under the age of 45, and in developed countries it often results in long-term sick leave (more than 90 lost working days) [6]. Risks for developing low back pain include age, body height, muscle weakness, previous episodes of back pain, obesity, and smoking. In contrast, occupational risks include jobs with frequent heavy lifting, exposure to vibration while driving, and a sedentary lifestyle [7]. Socio-demographic factors, such as gender and sedentary work at a computer education, also play a significant role — particularly in the diagnosis of lower anxiety. Psychosocial and physical risk factors can

contribute to the onset of a first episode of low back pain or the transition to chronic pain [8].

Degenerative changes of the intervertebral joints cause in most cases (about 85%), lumbar pain, while less common causes are intervertebral disc prolapse (1-3%), spondylolisthesis, tumors, secondary tumor deposits (about 1%), compression fractures of the thoracolumbar segment (4%) and infections, such as tuberculous spondylodiscitis (1-5%). Inflammatory diseases of the lumbar spine, such as ankylosing spondylitis, are also causative [8, 9]. The causes of lumbar pain are divided into three basic groups:

- Spinal mechanical causes, including sprains, degenerative diseases, spondylolisthesis, spinal canal stenosis, and congenital deformities.
- Spinal non-degenerative causes tumors, infections, and inflammatory diseases.
- Extraspinal causes, which include pelvic diseases (prostatitis, endometriosis), renal diseases (nephrolithiasis, pyelonephritis), vascular diseases (aortic aneurysm) and gastrointestinal disorders (cholecystitis, pancreatitis). This classification enables a more precise approach to lumbar pain.

Methods

The methodological framework of the research in the work is subordinated to the subject, the structure of the work, and the achievement of the set goals. The research used a systematic literature review methodology based on the PRISMA Method (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses - PRISMA), using clear and predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Databases such as Web of Knowledge, Scholar, and Science Direct will be accessed to search for scientific literature in English and other regional languages.

A detailed analysis of the most effective rehabilitation techniques for lumbar syndrome. Understanding the importance of an individual approach in the treatment of patients. Recommendations for a rehabilitation program that can help reduce symptoms and prevent relapse.

Emphasis on the importance of educating patients on proper movement techniques, ergonomics, and adaptation of daily activities to reduce the risk of recurrent lumbar spine pain. The research was conducted in November 2024. The literature review includes articles from studies published in the last 10 years.

Clinical guidelines

According to a systematic analysis of the global burden of disease conducted by Vos et al., lumbar pain is among the ten leading diseases and injuries with the highest number of DALYs (disease-adjusted life years, a measure of the total burden of disease adopted by the World Health Organization, which expresses years lost due to disease, disability or early death) [10]. This underscores the importance of increasing awareness about this issue. Good clinical practice guidelines are defined as guidelines that represent "systematically developed statements (evidence) to assist physicians and patients in making decisions about appropriate health care for specific clinical circumstances" [11]. These clinical guidelines respond to contemporary challenges, such as the rapid expansion of medical knowledge, and support the implementation of evidence-based medicine.

These guidelines aim to define the optimal decisions for most patients in everyday clinical situations without the intention of replacing the physician's independent judgment in specific cases. The guidelines allow for the application of evidence-based medicine through comparative effectiveness research results, focusing on providing the best possible care to patients [12].

The ideal scenario implies that expert panels develop clinical recommendations systematically with access to available evidence, an understanding of clinical challenges, and significant experience in evaluating procedures and relevant research methods. These panels should make decisions based on sound evidence, and they must be objective and independent so that the guidelines are up-to-date, impartial, and free from conflicts of interest.

According to contemporary foreign literature, guidelines recommend the implementation of diagnostic triage, which includes the classification of patients into three groups: those with non-specific lumbar pain, those with suspected severe pathology, known as "red flags" (such as malignancy, infection, or injury), and those with radiculopathy. The German guide also introduces an additional classification for patients with an increased risk of transitioning to a chronic condition, using the "yellow flags" [13]. All guides agree that diagnostic procedures should be focused on recognizing "red flags" and ruling out specific diseases. Examples of "red flags" include age under 20 or over 55, unexplained weight loss, and progressive neurological symptoms. However, guidelines vary between physical examinations and specific diagnostic tests [14].

Clinical symptoms

The European guideline recommends focusing on musculoskeletal examination, including inspection, assessment of spinal range of motion, palpation, identification of functional limitations, and neurological examination. Although the components of neurological screening are not always clearly defined, where they are listed, they include assessment of muscle strength, reflexes, sensation, and the leg-raised test [15].

Lumbar syndrome includes a wide range of clinical symptoms that are primarily manifested by pain in the lower back. The pain can be localized or spread to one or both legs, most often along the dermatome, characteristic of radiculopathy. In addition to pain, patients frequently report a feeling of stiffness, reduced range of motion, and discomfort when sitting, standing, frequently pulsate, or doing physical activity [16].

Neuropathic symptoms, such as tingling, burning, or loss of sensation in the legs, may occur in patients with nerve root compression. In more severe cases, such as cauda equina syndrome, lower limb muscle weakness, incontinence, or bowel dysfunction occur, indicating severe damage to the nervous system [16]. Musculoskele-

tal symptoms include muscle spasms in the lumbar region, reduced flexibility, and a feeling of tension. These symptoms are often more pronounced after prolonged rest or physical exertion. In some patients, the pain may be pulsating and worsen at night, suggesting potential inflammatory processes [17]. Functional limitations are common and include difficulty bending, lifting objects, or walking long distances. Patients often report changes in posture, which may become asymmetrical or unnatural due to attempts to reduce pain [18].

Psychosomatic manifestations, such as fatigue, irritability, and anxiety, often accompany chronic forms of lumbar syndrome, further deteriorating the overall quality of life for patients. In specific cases, like Bertolotti's syndrome, pain arises from anomalies of the transitional vertebrae, frequently accompanied by changes in pelvic mobility. Radiculopathy caused by annular ruptures may also lead to sexual dysfunction and pelvic pain [19].

Clinical examination

Clinical examination includes neurologic assessment of muscle strength, reflexes, and sensation, while the leg-raised test helps identify radiculopathy caused by nerve root compression. Radiological methods, such as X-ray, CT, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), play a key role in visualizing structural abnormalities, including disc herniation and spinal stenosis. Specific syndromes, such as Bertolotti's, require detailed radiological evaluation due to their association with transitional vertebral anomalies. Electroneuromyography (EMNG) is an additional method that enables identification of neurological damage and differentiation of musculoskeletal from neurological causes of pain [20]. In patients with chronic symptoms, it is also recommended to assess psychosocial factors, such as depression, that may contribute to the intensity and duration of pain. In cases where systemic or infectious causes are suspected, laboratory tests, including inflammation and infection markers analyses, are beneficial. The differential diagnosis should include considering rare enti-

ties, such as annular ruptures or spinal tumors, which may present with nonspecific pain. When metabolic disorders like osteoporosis or Cushing's syndrome are suspected, densitometry and hormonal analyses are necessary [21].

Drug therapy

An integrated approach involving a multidisciplinary team of specialists is essential for successfully diagnosing and treating lumbar syndrome, particularly in patients with complex symptoms and multiple comorbidities. Lumbar syndrome, one of the leading causes of lower back pain, requires a tailored approach to drug treatment. The primary goals of therapy are to alleviate pain, control inflammation, and enhance the functional status of patients. First-line therapy typically involves nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), such as ibuprofen, diclofenac, or naproxen, which effectively reduce inflammation and relieve pain. NSAIDs are beneficial during the acute phase, but their long-term use may be limited due to gastrointestinal and cardiovascular side effects. Selective cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitors, like celecoxib, are often favored in such instances. For patients experiencing muscle spasms, muscle relaxants such as tizanidine and baclofen have significantly reduced muscle tone and pain [22]. These muscle relaxants are particularly effective when combined with NSAIDs for patients with acute pain episodes. For those with severe pain, where NSAIDs and muscle relaxants are insufficient, tramadol and tapentadol are utilized as moderate-strength analgesics. They are preferred over traditional opioids due to their lower risk of addiction. However, in cases of extremely severe pain, opioids such as morphine or oxycodone may be included in the treatment plan, but with stringent monitoring and limited duration. In instances of neuropathic pain, which is common in radiculopathy, anticonvulsants like gabapentin and pregabalin are critical [22]. These medications function by modulating the neurons, transmitting pain signals, and alleviating neuropathy symptoms. Antidepressants, particularly tricyclic antidepressants such as

amitriptyline and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors like duloxetine, are also employed in patients experiencing chronic pain. These drugs not only help manage pain but also positively influence patients' moods, which is especially important for those facing psychosocial challenges [23]. Recent studies highlight the potential of phosphodiesterase two inhibitors as a promising therapy for treating degenerative spine diseases. These medications operate at the molecular level, diminishing tissue inflammatory processes [24].

Physiotherapy

Kinesiotherapy is essential in rehabilitating patients with lumbar syndrome, as it combines targeted exercises and movements to alleviate pain, enhance mobility, and improve muscle stability. The primary objective of kinesiotherapy is to boost patients' functionality and prevent the recurrence of symptoms. Exercise programs concentrate on strengthening the deep trunk muscles, particularly the transversus abdominis and multifidus, which provide stability to the spine. These exercises have proven effective in reducing pain and enhancing functional capacity in patients with nonspecific low back pain [25]. Dynamic stretching exercises are also beneficial for enhancing the flexibility of the lumbar region and alleviating muscle tension. Extension exercises, which include gentle back bending movements, have been proven effective in increasing mobility and relieving pressure on nerve roots in patients with herniated discs. These exercises are particularly advantageous when combined with physical therapy techniques. In patients experiencing radiculopathy or numb sciatica, targeted exercises that relieve tension on the sciatic nerve significantly reduce pain and enhance mobility [26]. A multidisciplinary approach that integrates physical therapy with patient education on proper body mechanics and ergonomics can reduce relapse rates and enhance long-term benefits. Hydrokinesiotherapy is a specific form of rehabilitation that utilizes therapeutic exercises in water and has proven to be an effective method for treating

lumbar syndrome. The therapeutic properties of water, such as reduced gravity and increased resistance, facilitate exercises and improve mobility [27]. The psychological effects of hydrokinesiotherapy are significant, as exercising in water provides patients with a sense of relaxation and alleviates stress related to chronic pain. This positively influences their motivation for rehabilitation. Hydrokinesiotherapy speeds up recovery, enhances muscle strength, and lowers the risk of pain recurrence in patients recovering from herniated disc surgery. Additionally, water exercises are more effective than land exercises in reducing pain and increasing flexibility in patients with lumbar stenosis [28]. Massage, manipulation, and mobilization are vital manual therapies for addressing lumbar syndrome, designed to reduce pain, improve functionality, and promote movement. Often, massage is the first step in therapy because it relaxes muscles and enhances circulation in the affected area, providing immediate pain relief and alleviating tension. Clinicians frequently use a combination of these techniques for a comprehensive treatment approach. Massage is particularly effective at relieving pain in patients dealing with muscle spasms and increased stiffness. Manipulation is recommended for those experiencing acute pain, while mobilization is preferred for patients with chronic pain and limited mobility [29]. Electrotherapy is an important component in managing lumbar syndrome, particularly for reducing pain and enhancing the functionality of patients. The primary methods of electrotherapy include transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), interference currents (IFC), electrical muscle stimulation (EMS), and laser therapy. TENS is widely used to alleviate acute and chronic pain by blocking pain signals at the spinal cord level and stimulating the release of endorphins. Interference currents enable electrical impulses to penetrate deeper into the tissue, leading to a significant decrease in pain for patients with non-specific low back pain. Electrical muscle stimulation is utilized to enhance muscle strength and improve spinal stability, especially in patients with diminished abdominal and back muscle tone [30]. Laser therapy, as part of elec-

trotherapy, shows significant effectiveness in reducing inflammation and accelerating tissue regeneration, benefiting patients with radiculopathy and disc herniation. Combining electrotherapy with kinesiotherapy produces better results in alleviating pain and enhancing patients' functional capacity compared to exercises alone [31]. Laser therapy is a modern approach for treating lumbar syndrome that utilizes low-level laser therapy (LLLT) or high-power laser therapy (HLLT) to alleviate pain, reduce inflammation, and enhance tissue regeneration. Low-level laser therapy is particularly effective at diminishing pain in patients with chronic non-specific back pain by acting at the cellular level to improve mitochondrial function and local circulation. A key benefit of HLLT is its ability to penetrate deeply into tissues, making it suitable for treating deep muscles and joint structures in the lumbar spine [32]. Heat therapy and cryotherapy are commonly used methods for treating lumbar syndrome due to their analgesic and regenerative properties. Heat therapy involves applying heat to affected areas to alleviate pain and enhance circulation, while cryotherapy applies cold to reduce inflammation and swelling. Applying heat to the lower back boosts blood flow, decreases muscle tension, and improves flexibility, which is particularly beneficial for those with chronic pain. This therapy is often combined with stretching exercises for optimal results. Conversely, cryotherapy lowers tissue metabolic activity, alleviates inflammation, and mitigates pain by inhibiting nerve impulses. The effectiveness of these therapies varies depending on the stage of the condition. Cryotherapy is recommended during acute phases for its ability to reduce inflammation, whereas heat therapy is more effective in chronic stages for relaxing muscles and enhancing mobility. Recent studies indicate that combining these therapies leads to significantly better outcomes than using either one alone. For example, alternating between cold and warm compresses enhances circulation and speeds up recovery. Cryotherapy can also be performed in the form of whole body cryotherapy (WBC), which exposes the body to extremely low temperatures to relieve pain and

promote tissue regeneration. Local cryotherapy using ice or gel packs is especially effective for acute pain and postoperative recovery. Heat therapy includes the use of warm compresses, infrared lamps, or thermal baths, all of which improve circulation and relax muscles. Long-term use of heat therapy is associated with better functional outcomes in patients with non-specific low back pain [33]. Patient education is a crucial part of the therapeutic approach to lumbar syndrome, as it empowers patients to understand their condition better and actively participate in their own treatment. The goal of education is to alleviate fear, enhance adherence to therapy, and promote healthy lifestyles. A primary focus of education is to inform patients about the nature of low back pain, including the differences between acute and chronic pain, as well as the impact of factors such as poor posture and lack of physical activity. Patients should also be made aware of the importance of regular exercise and maintaining an optimal body weight. Group educational programs that include discussions with therapists and fellow patients have been shown to effectively reduce pain perception and anxiety in individuals with chronic low back syndrome. These programs provide support and motivation, which are essential for the long-term management of the condition. Practical education, such as demonstrating proper lifting techniques and making ergonomic adjustments in the workplace, helps prevent the recurrence of symptoms. Studies indicate that patients who receive education about body mechanics are at a lower risk of experiencing pain relapse [34, 35].

Future therapies and action plans

Regenerative medicine utilizes autologous or allogenic biologics to assist the body in repairing itself by replacing or restoring damaged tissue. As a relatively new medical subspecialty, it should be approached with professional caution, although regenerative methods appear to hold promise. Limited evidence exists to support regenerative therapies for treating certain types of LBP [36]. Chronic pain should be viewed as a

biopsychosocial phenomenon rather than merely a sensory one. Therefore, it is important to ask LBP patients about their lifestyle, social situation, employment, current stressors, diet, use of alcohol and other substances, family dynamics, and health habits [37]. By reconceptualizing pain and discussing it in the context of the patient's broader life, the patient may feel more empowered during the rehabilitation process. Naturally, the pandemic drastically altered rehabilitation practices. During the lockdown period, telerehabilitation became a viable option [38]. Software applications (like smartphone apps) can connect patients with clinics or clinical services to monitor their progress or answer questions.

Low back pain (LBP) remains a global health challenge, but our increasing understanding of its complex causes, multimodal drug therapies, interventional procedures, and recent advancements may improve future treatments and help restore function and comfort to the many LBP patients seeking relief care.

Conclusion

Lumbar syndrome is one of the most common and socioeconomically significant health issues in modern society. Lower back pain significantly affects patients' quality of life, work capacity, and functional independence while straining healthcare systems due to high diagnostic and treatment costs. Given the multifactorial nature of lumbar syndrome, which encompasses biomechanical, psychosocial, and systemic factors, an integrated approach to treatment is crucial for achieving optimal results. Patient education plays an essential role in the therapeutic process as it fosters better adherence to therapy and encourages patients to actively participate in their recovery. Furthermore, employing modern methods such as electrotherapy, hydrokinesotherapy, and laser therapy has led to significant advances in treating lumbar syndrome, reducing the need for invasive interventions. In the future, further research should concentrate on developing new technologies and therapeutic protocols while monitoring the effects of various

long-term treatments. Emphasizing prevention through education and promoting healthy lifestyles can help lower the prevalence of lumbar syndrome and its consequences.

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